

A simple relation between the proton rest energy and charge radius, accurate within experimental errors

Abstract: We report a very simple mathematical relation between the proton rest energy and charge radius which is accurate within experimental errors, and appears to be a variant of the uncertainty principle. We apply this result to show that if each gluon inside a proton is attributed a constituent share of the proton's total rest energy, the width of each gluon, owing to its confinement, is equal to its constituent energy.

Obtaining a precise value for the proton charge radius has been a challenge over the past decade owing to a discrepancy of 5.6 standard deviations between electronic and muonic measurements. This led to the so-called proton charge radius puzzle, see [1] at page 6. However, new electronic measurements [2] appear to have resolved that puzzle, and are accounted for in the present PDG value $r_p = 0.8409 \pm 0.0004$ fm, [1], page 7. The proton rest energy on the other hand has long been known with good precision, and the latest PDG data [1] at page 1 lists this at $m_p c^2 = 938.2720813 \pm 0.0000058$ MeV. Here we show a very simple mathematical relation between the proton rest energy and charge radius which is accurate within experimental errors, and appears to be a variant of the uncertainty principle.

In 2019, NIST revised its measurement standards by adding Planck's constant h and several others to the speed of light c as having exact, defined values. The reduced $\hbar = h / 2\pi$ is therefore exact to any number of decimal places when using π to the same number of places. Thus, to ten places in GeV, the conversion constant $\hbar c = 0.1973269804$ GeV · fm, see PDG's [3]. It turns out that this is interrelated with the above proton rest energy and charge radius within experimental errors by:

$$\frac{1}{4} m_p c^2 r_p = \hbar c. \quad (1)$$

For, if one carries out a very simple calculation using $\hbar c$ and $E_p = m_p c^2$ above, one finds from (1) that the proton charge radius, which is the least-tightly-known of the above empirical data, is:

$$r_p = 4\hbar c / E_p = 0.841235648 \pm 0.000000005 \text{ fm}. \quad (2)$$

This, one can see, fits within the experimental error bounds of $0.8405 \leq r_p \leq 0.8413$, and is more accurate by a factor of about 800,000.

Moreover, it is well-known that the uncertainty principle may be written in terms of energies and lengths as $\Delta E \Delta r \geq \frac{1}{2} \hbar c$. In this manner, (1) may be written as:

$$E_p r_p = 4\hbar c \geq \frac{1}{2} \hbar c. \quad (3)$$

In this form, (1) appears to be a statement of how the uncertainty principle which limits the simultaneous observation of conjugate variables, specifically applies to the proton rest energy and charge radius. This raises the prospect of a direct connection between the uncertainty principle, and the quantum chromodynamic (QCD) confinement of individual particles with net color charges, such as quarks and gluons. For example:

Constituent quark masses attribute approximately 1/3 of the proton rest energy to the dressing of current quarks with a sea of gluons and virtual quarks. However, the adjoint representation of the gauge group $SU(3)_{\text{QCD}}$ gives rise to $8 = 3^2 - 1$ gluonic gauge bosons in $A^\mu = \frac{1}{2} \lambda_i A_i^\mu$ where λ_i with $i = 1 \dots 8$ are the Gell-Mann matrices. And this is the same ratio of 8 by which $4\hbar c$ exceeds the (Gaussian) minimum $\frac{1}{2} \hbar c$ in (3). So, we may attribute a "constituent" energy $E_{Gi} \equiv \frac{1}{8} E_p$ by definition to each of the eight bi-colored gluons A_i^μ such that $\sum_{i=1}^8 E_{Gi} = E_p$. Then we may write (3) in terms of these constituent gluon energies as:

$$E_{Gi} r_p = \frac{1}{2} \hbar c. \quad (4)$$

Next, with τ_i denoting the mean lifetime of each gluon, let us also attribute a full width $\Gamma_{iG} = \hbar / \tau_i = \hbar c / c\tau_i$ to each of these gluons. Because each gluon is confined within the proton, we use the proton charge diameter

$d_p = 2r_p$ to establish a mean luminous propagation range $c\tau_i = d_p = 2r_p$ for each gluon. Used in (4), this now yields, for *each* gluon, with no implied index summation:

$$E_{Gi}c\tau_i = \hbar c. \quad (5)$$

If we then substitute the foregoing gluon widths $c\tau_i = \hbar c / \Gamma_{iG}$ into (5), constants $\hbar c$ appear on each side of the equation, so that following reduction we obtain the simple relation:

$$E_{Gi} = \Gamma_{iG} = \frac{1}{8} E_p. \quad (6)$$

Thus, owing to their confinement, each gluon has a width equal to its constituent energy. Taken with $\sum_{i=1}^8 E_{Gi} = E_p$ upon which the derivation of (6) was predicated, we learn that although each $E_{Gi} = \frac{1}{8} E_p$, each gluon also has an equally-large width whereby the individual constituent gluon energies may fluctuate greatly from this central E_{Gi} , while the overall $E_p = \sum_{i=1}^8 E_{Gi}$ is maintained so that when summed together these constituent gluons yield a definite, stable proton with $E_p = m_p c^2 = 938.2720813 \pm 0.0000058 \text{ MeV}$.

To summarize: the empirical data for the proton rest energy and charge radius satisfy the simple mathematical relation (1) within experimental errors as seen in (2), which takes the form of an uncertainty relation (3) for the proton. If we then subdivide the proton rest energy into constituent contributions from the eight gluons rather than the three quarks, we learn that each gluon has a width equal to its energy as seen in (6). So, the internal dynamics of the proton allow for large fluctuations in the constituent energy carried by any single confined gluon, while the total rest energy of the complete proton remains fixed and definite.

References

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- [1] P.A. Zyla et al. (Particle Data Group), Prog. Theor. Exp. Phys. 2020, 083C01 (2020) and 2021 update, <https://pdg.lbl.gov/2021/listings/rpp2021-list-p.pdf>.
- [2] Xiong, W., Gasparian, A., Gao, H. et al., *A small proton charge radius from an electron–proton scattering experiment*, Nature **575**, 147–150 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-019-1721-2>.
- [3] <https://pdg.lbl.gov/2021/reviews/rpp2020-rev-phys-constants.pdf>.